

**X SEMINARIO
IBEROAMERICANO CTS
XIV SEMINARIO IBÉRICO**
CTS Y CIUDADANÍAS: REFLEXIONES
POR UNA AGENDA EDUCATIVA
BOGOTÁ-COLOMBIA
JULIO 22-24 DE 2026

Separata:
Memorias X SEMINARIO IBEROAMERICANO
CTS / XIV SEMINARIO IBÉRICO CTS en Tecné,
Episteme y Didaxis: TED
No. 61, Primer semestre de 2027
ISSN:2665-3184 (impreso);2323-0126(web)

Digital Educational Platforms in Middle School: A STS and Inclusive Education Perspective

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Thematic Track: Interdisciplinarity and Knowledge Dialogue from an STS Perspective.

ABSTRACT. This study analyzes the impact of digital educational platforms in the final years of middle school from a Science, Technology, and Society (STS) perspective and inclusive education for students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), through a systematic literature review. The results indicate that tools such as Kahoot, GeoGebra, and Canva foster engagement and interactivity. However, from an STS perspective, technology is understood as neither neutral nor inherently inclusive. To support emancipatory processes in Specialized Educational Services, its use requires pedagogical intentionality and critical mediation, as well as teacher training to adapt platforms, avoid sensory overload, and respect cognitive diversity.

KEYWORDS. Autism Spectrum Disorder, Specialized Educational Services, Teacher Education, Digital Educational Platforms.

INTRODUCTION

The current generation of students demonstrates affinity with technological devices from the early stages of their education, which requires continuous adaptations in teaching to align the Brazilian educational process with the guidelines of the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) (Brazil, 2017). In this context, the implementation of digital educational platforms can provide a more dynamic, accessible, and effective learning environment.

For technology to use to go beyond an instrumental perspective, it is essential to analyze it

through the lens of Science, Technology, and Society (STS), which adopts a critical and contextualized view, considering ethical, social, and cultural implications. In education, this approach aims to develop autonomous, critical individuals who respect diversity and are capable of active participation in society (Almeida et al., 2024; Raiol et al., 2024).

This discussion becomes even more relevant when directed toward the context of Specialized Educational Services and practices aimed at the inclusion of students with Special Educational Needs, especially those with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). In this sense, science and technology education, when grounded in an STS perspective, has the potential to break down barriers and ableist attitudes, providing these students with equitable opportunities for developing critical thinking and citizenship (Raiol et al., 2024).

Thus, this study aims to investigate the impact of using digital educational platforms in Middle School (final years) through a Systematic Literature Review (SLR), articulating its findings with the STS perspective and discussing the challenges and potential of these tools in the context of inclusive education and Specialized Educational Services.

SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW PROTOCOL

A systematic literature review is an evidence-based methodological approach aimed at collecting, categorizing, evaluating, and synthesizing the results of relevant studies on a specific topic (Flick, 2012; Kitchenham & Brereton, 2013). It differs from traditional reviews by following a rigorous methodology designed to minimize bias at all stages of the process, from the search and selection of studies to the critical analysis of findings and data synthesis, while also enabling replication by the scientific community (Coutinho, 2014).

Research Questions

This systematic literature review aims to investigate educational platforms designed for middle school students (final years of elementary education), exploring their impact on pedagogical practices and on the development of students' competencies.

The initial phase of the systematic review consisted of the careful selection of scientific articles that addressed the research questions (Flick, 2012). To define these questions, as well as the search terms, the PICO protocol was used, which represents the essential elements of a research question: Patient/Problem, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome. This acronym is widely used in scientific research to structure clinical or research questions in a way that optimizes the search and selection of relevant evidence (Kitchenham & Brereton, 2013).

By outlining these components, the PICO protocol supports the precise formulation of research questions, facilitating the identification of relevant studies during the systematic review. This structured approach contributes to the effectiveness of the review process, ensuring a comprehensive and rigorous analysis of the available literature.

Thus, four research questions (RQ) were defined, one primary (RQ1) and three secondary, as follows:

RQ1 – What digital educational platforms are reported, and what is the impact of their use in

middle school (final years of elementary education)?

RQ2 – Do educational platforms influence the quality of teaching and student learning?

RQ3 – How do students behave when using educational platforms?

RQ4 – What are teachers' perceptions regarding their experience with the use of educational platforms?

Search Strategy

The search terms defined for retrieving primary studies in the selected databases, along with their variations, were: (“educational platforms” OR “educational platform” OR “digital platform” OR “digital platforms”) AND “elementary education” AND “final years.”

The databases selected for the search were: CAPES Journals Portal (Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel)¹ Google Scholar², RENOTE³ - Journal of New Technologies in Education, SCIELO⁴ - *Scientific Electronic Library Online* and SOL⁵ – SBC OpenLib (Brazilian Computer Society Digital Library), with a specific focus on educational platforms.

The search period covered studies published from 2017 onward. This choice is based on the year of implementation of the Brazilian National Common Curricular Base (BNCC), which aims to improve pedagogical practices by promoting the effective use of educational technologies to meet educational goals and prepare students for an ever-evolving context, where proficiency in digital skills has become essential (Brazil, 2017).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The following Inclusion Criteria (IC) and Exclusion Criteria (EC) were established.

Inclusion Criteria:

IC1 – Studies that investigate the use of digital educational platforms in middle school (final years of elementary education);

IC2 – Studies that evaluate the quality of teaching, student performance, and teacher satisfaction based on their perspectives;

IC3 – Primary studies published from 2017 to the present;

IC4 – Peer-reviewed studies;

IC5 – Studies available in Portuguese.

Exclusion Criteria:

EC1 – Duplicate studies;

EC2 – Studies with restricted or unavailable access;

EC3 – Studies that do not address the main research question (RQ1).

¹ <https://www-periodicos-capes-gov-br.ez1.periodicos.capes.gov.br>

² <https://scholar.google.pt/schhp?hl=pt-BR>

³ <https://seer.ufrgs.br/renote>

⁴ <https://www.scielo.br>

⁵ <https://sol.sbc.org.br>

Conducting the Systematic Literature Review

The selection of relevant studies constitutes a fundamental pillar of this systematic review, which began in September 2023. The initial search yielded a total of 757 potential studies. Subsequently, the inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied, resulting in the selection of the articles to be analyzed, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Search Results in the Databases

BASE	CAPE	GOOGLE SCHOLAR	RENOTE	SCIELO	SOL	TOTAL
Relevant Studies	329	323	26	43	36	757

Source: The Authors (2026)

After conducting the searches in the selected databases, the 757 studies were subjected to the exclusion criteria, resulting in the exclusion of 118 studies and the selection of 639. This total was then subjected to the inclusion criteria, resulting in 614 exclusions and 25 studies selected for the next stage.

In the second stage, the primary studies were read in full to determine whether they were capable of addressing RQ1. Out of the 25 studies, 21 were excluded, and 4 studies were selected for the snowballing and data extraction stage. At this stage, the inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied again; however, no additional studies were identified for inclusion.

Table 2 presents the search sources used and the corresponding number of articles selected in each database after the completion of the screening stages.

Table 2. Articles Selected After the Systematic Review Stages

	CAPE	GOOGLE SCHOLAR	RENOTE	SCIELO	SOL
Articles Identified Using Search Terms	329	323	26	43	36
Articles Selected After Abstract Screening	9	16	0	0	0
Articles Selected After Full-Text Review	3	1	0	0	0

Source: The Authors (2026)

Figure 1 shows the number of articles selected after the systematic review analysis.

Figure 1: Articles Selected After the Systematic Review Stages

Source: The Authors (2026)

SELECTED PAPERS

Table 3. Selected Articles

ID	Year	Title	Authors
EP1	2017	Kahoot and GoConqr: Use of educational games for teaching mathematics	Tiago Romio, Simone Cristine Mendes Paiva
EP2	2018	Making sense of mathematics learning using blended learning models	Adriane Carrilho Esperança Vergara, Verlaní Timm Hinz, João Ladislau Barbará Lopes
EP3	2021	An experience using the Hypatiamat platform to teach the Pythagorean theorem	Ruth Leia Pereira de Farias, Mariana Pelissari Monteiro Aguiar Baroni
EP4	2021	Digital technologies in teaching plane geometry: An experience report with an 8th-grade class	Daiane da Silva Fagundes, Denice Aparecida Fontana Menegais, Kérolyn Avila Polvora Soares

Source: The Authors (2026)

THE INTERPLAY OF STS AND SPECIAL EDUCATION

To deepen the theoretical and conceptual framework, it is imperative to comprehend the integration of digital educational platforms through the interdisciplinary lens of Science, Technology, and Society (STS) (Almeida et al., 2024; Raiol et al., 2024). Historically, technology in education has often been viewed through a positivist and linear model, where tools are seen merely as neutral providers of practical benefits (Almeida et al., 2024). However, the STS perspective challenges this instrumentalist view, positing that scientific and technological literacy must be socially and environmentally contextualized to promote democratic participation (Raiol et al., 2024). In the realm of Special Education and Specialized Educational Services (AEE), adopting this critical stance is fundamental to dismantling ableist barriers and overcoming prejudice (Raiol et al., 2024). It shifts the educational focus from merely training students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) to operate software, toward cultivating their autonomy, critical thinking, and respect for diversity, grounded in ethical values (Almeida et al., 2024).

Consequently, the role of digital educational platforms transcends content delivery, acting as a catalyst for the construction of critical citizens committed to contemporary challenges (Raiol et al., 2024). When educational technologies, such as Kahoot, GeoGebra, or Canva, are mediated with pedagogical intentionality, they allow students with ASD to engage actively with their learning environment, honoring their unique cognitive and sensory profiles (Felisberto, 2024). This STS-driven mediation empowers neurodivergent students to transition from passive recipients of information to active agents of change within their communities (Almeida et al., 2024). By contextualizing abstract concepts within broader social realities, the STS framework ensures that inclusive education fosters true social participation, preparing students to negotiate decisions related to science and technology in modern society (Raiol et al., 2024).

To visually synthesize these dynamics and address the need for a stronger conceptual representation, the diagram of Figure 2 illustrates the complex interplay between the core elements of this study. It maps how the STS triad converges with inclusive pedagogical practices and critical teacher mediation to transform digital platforms into emancipatory tools, ultimately culminating in the formation of critical and engaged citizens.

Figure 2: Convergence of the STS framework, digital platforms, and inclusive pedagogical mediation for the formation of critical citizens.

Source: The Authors (2026)

ADDITIONAL CONCLUSIONS

Furthermore, the effectiveness of digital educational platforms in fostering inclusive education is intrinsically linked to institutional conditions and teacher autonomy (Souza & Rossi, 2023). The compulsory or top-down adoption of these tools, without considering the specificities of each school context or providing adequate structural and technical support, often limits their

emancipatory potential (Gatti, 2010; Nóvoa, 2009). To transcend the mere instrumental use of technology, it is crucial to integrate these digital resources into the student's Individualized Educational Plan (PEI) (Mendes, 2006). This strategic alignment ensures that platforms are not treated as universal solutions, but rather as adaptable pedagogical instruments that respect the neurodivergent learning profiles and specific goals of students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD).

Finally, future research and public policies must prioritize continuous teacher education that intertwines technical proficiency with critical inclusive practices and the STS (Science, Technology, and Society) philosophy (Almeida et al., 2024; Reis & Coutinho, 2022). Overcoming the barriers of sensory overload and the lack of accessible features requires collaborative efforts among educators, developers, and policymakers (Nascimento et al., 2020; Viana & Manrique, 2023). By empowering teachers to critically mediate and adapt these digital environments, schools can transform technology into a genuine catalyst for equity. Ultimately, the inclusive power of digital platforms emerges not from the tools themselves, but from the intentional, humanized, and socially contextualized pedagogical practices that guide their application (Kenski, 2018; Moran, 2000; Raiol et al., 2024).

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